

THE EFFECT OF THE INTERNET ON CHILDREN'S THINKING

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Annotation. The 21st-century world is changing and rapidly developing in colorful fields. It's no secret that new changes and new ways are being appended to people's commerce and trade of ideas, mastering and serving business. Most of the new techniques are mainly in the hands of our youth. The majority of the population is also young people, and they communicate with each other through social networks, exchange ideas, and share their creations with others.

Keywords: youth, knowledge, social, active, cerebral, knowledge, Islam, culture and tradition, Internet, individual, society, evolution, art:

Youth activity refers to the manifestation of internal and external trends in social life. Social activity is the main expression of a person's position as a person and is a quality index. Consequently, gregarious exertion is an important and native portion of a person. Youth exertion is related to the operation of his life and the incarnation of valuations. Social activity is the main expression of the position of a person as a person, a system of satisfying his high requirements and a quality index. In this reference, the activity of a person is studied in political broad and fragile (narrow) Social activity situations. The study of a person in similar situations acquires methodological significance.¹

Every stage of human life is vital. Among these important stages, the youth stage of life is of personal significance. Youth is the most sensitive period in a person's life. Youth is the time when a person is full of dynamism and has swelled mobility. At the same time, the period of youth is also the time when a person stands at the crossroads of life paths. If at that crossroads, a person enters a good path, he will turn to a great good for himself, his family, relatives, people, and country. However, if this path is a bad path for his family and surrounding people, as well as for his people and country, he has taken a step towards an extremely disappointing event².

If we take into account that young people are the future of every country, the importance of paying attention to them has increased even more. The identity of each person becomes clear from his youth, and his majority begins from his youth. Social activism is currently developing rapidly and intensively. Today, the level of social activity of our youth has changed over the past five years, and the period of social depression and indifference to reforms has passed. In a word, social networks have strengthened social activity and attracted the population to youthful people. As a result, youthful people are invariably exposed to colorful foreign ideas.

Discussion and results.

The social activity of young people makes up a large part of society compared to other layers. As a result, it causes various problems. First of all, this is because the situation of youthful people in society is not completely formed. youthful people enter social structures, that is, they

¹ Tursunova N. Social activity of young people: concepts and qualities. "Social opinion". 2004. No. 3. Pages 149-150.

² Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf "Social manners" 2023 page 153.

witness the process of socialization. Social activism can be understood as a person's trouble to contribute to the evolution of society and its future, regardless of what profession or situation a person holds. Social activism is a complex process that can be completed in one day or the first stages of social activity begin in kindergarten, and the most important period is the period of social formation during the pupil period when it is delicate for him to take a professional and detect his position moment.

Today, modern tools based on information and communication technologies have occupied an important part of our lives. In particular, social networks have become the most important and indispensable means of communication between humanity, along with the acceleration of globalization processes. Currently, 63% of the entire population uses the Internet.

The number of Internet users has increased by 200 million in a period of almost 1 year. The majority of Internet users (92.4%) use the Internet through mobile devices. 4.65 billion users actively use social networks. These figures show once again how important the online world is. There are further than 3 billion people utilizing couriers worldwide.

The platforms with the most users are Facebook and WhatsApp exercised by further than 2.5 billion users. Inactivity and public couriers are also exercised in several advanced nations. involving Line in Japan, KakaoTalk in South Korea, and WeChat in China.

Statista.com published a list of the most popular couriers

WhatsApp has further than 2 billion users

Weixin/ Wechat(China) — around 1.3 billion users

Facebook Messenger — has 988 million users

QQ — 574 mln. users

Snapchat — 557 mln. users

Telegram — 550 mln. users

More than 100 billion messages are sent from the messenger in one day;

On average, the app is used for 38 minutes per day via mobile devices;

The share of users aged 26–35 is 27%;

46.1% of users are women;

The list of the most popular messengers in Uzbekistan is as follows:

Telegram — 80% of users

WhatsApp — 22% of users

Facebook Messenger — 6% of users

According to datareportal.com, about 70% of the population of Uzbekistan are internet users. 18.3% of the population use social networks.³

Instagram is the most used social network by users in our country. Currently, the number of users of this network is more than 4.8 million. 34.4% of users are women. The majority of users are young people (18–35 years old).

In Uzbekistan, various works have been carried out on the creation of national messengers and social networks. According to [Kun. uz](https://kun.uz), the national social network [davra. uz](https://davra.uz) was created in 2016, and the number of its subscribers today is 22,500. This indicator of 6 years shows that the network has not been popularized. In addition, in 2016, a network called «Uchar» appeared and

³ <https://datareportal.com/global-digital-overview>

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was not popular. In addition, in 2018, the UzChat messenger belonging to «UMS» LLC was launched, but it did not become popular. In 2011, the messenger «diaysuk.uz» was also created and discontinued in 2018. The main reasons for the lack of popularity of national messengers are the lack of cyber security, reliable data storage, and stable performance. Many created platforms are installed on home or office servers, and when the number of users reaches several thousand, there are interruptions in operation. Nowadays, special attention is paid to these factors when creating social networks.

A total of 24.1 million in our country. there are internet users. These numbers are growing by an average of 1.4% per year. In addition, 28.5% of the population is between 18–35 years old and actively uses social networks, including messengers.⁴ The rapid-fire evolution of the country, the acquirement of certain accomplishments, the substance of the people, the confidence in the future, and the bold way taken by the head of the country towards a thing are the possessors of the future of that country, that is, the instruction and parenting of the youth. and depends on the position of concentration paid to the future. Youth effects and their cases are one of the most priority directions of the country procedure of Uzbekistan. The first socialization of a child starts from the child's kindergarten period. He falls into a new environment away from his parents and loved ones. In this terrain, the child doesn't join anyone in the first days and behaves like a stranger, and this period begins the period of compliance. During the observation period, he also learned about the environment and behavior. Gradually, communication and friends among children begin to increase. If children cannot find friends around them, then they may be facing psychological problems. The child will be separated from his peers. Educators must observe children and organize games to solve their problems. A psychological and pedagogical approach is necessary. Interest in studying the social activity of adolescents as a psychological and pedagogical phenomenon is connected with the presence of representatives of this age group due to their psychophysiological characteristics, desire and desire to perform socially significant actions. The mobility of the value system, promotion of the need to expand the social space, self-defense among peers and attention to the approval of others, self-awareness as a personality, and other characteristics characteristic of adolescents, children of this age school, make the family the weakest and most attractive part of society. The future begins moment. In our country, all the conditions have been created for young people to get and become ripe individualities in all aspects. This composition aims to reflect on the conditioning, social mores, and mores of utilizing the Internet network, which is formed as a result of applying theoretically acquired knowledge to exercise. We set it as a thing. The conception of social activism is nearly related to the conception of civil society. The main thing in studying citizenship and civil knowledge is studying civil activism to erect a civil society. After all, civil society is established not only by employing conscious subjects with citizenship characteristics but also by active subjects It is this activity that allows us to understand the general and private laws of the establishment of society.

Civic consciousness serves to unify the society, it serves to create an agreement between citizens in the way of common interests. Finds the contrary. currently, we can know movable bias similar to phones, tablets, computers, and analogous particulars in the hands of each of our young people. The Internet networks have helped boost the position of social activity among youthful people and speed up the process of collective message and news viewing. The word« Internet» is

⁴ <https://mininnovation.uz/ru/news/post-745>

an abbreviated judgment in a foreign language, which means «transnational data network» in our language. It is not limited, but it has become useful for carrying out more voluminous-scale work. In all areas of our lives, the advantages of release, stinginess, and celerity are discerned with the help of the Internet. The Internet also works both ways it is getting commodities that can serve both good and bad. Our task is to educate youthful people on the good sides and mores of utilizing it. We should give non-identical exemplifications of the bad sides. To help young people from bordering on colorful foreign ideas, it is necessary to develop their unsubstantial knowledge, to be under the supervision of their parents, and to help them from bordering on terrorist groups. A person who wants to exercise the Internet should first of all have a good intention and set the right thing. Why do I want to pierce the Internet and how will it affect my future? Before accessing the Internet, one should save time for unnecessary things, learn the necessary knowledge and skills, and news, remember the value of one's life, think that every moment counts and this period will never return. It is precisely because of the lack of these qualities that many of our young people spend hours and hours of their precious lives on the Internet looking at unnecessary things. In addition, playing for hours on end makes young children forget their daily lifestyle, causing various health problems. Distances are appearing between friends, parents, and relatives. Mobile communication tools have brought In extension, rollicking for hours on end makes young children forget their diurnal life, causing colorful health cases. Distances are appearing between musketeers, parents, and cousins. Mobile message tools have brought us closer, but the passion for love between people has also dropped. Before accessing the Internet, you should make a well-budgeted work plan. As in any job, you should work on the base of a well-budgeted plan when utilizing the Internet. The intended area must be clear and the time of use must also be easily indicated. This in turn saves practice and time. «What should I do?», «What news is there in the world?» Who bought what sort of new auto?» will reduce perturbation. Thus, we should form the chops of utilizing social networks in our youth from a youthful time. In conclusion, the moment Internet networks have become a portion of our lives, it is necessary to seek a useful purpose in communicating with others through the Internet and shake unworkable conditioning. We must be around him more, to support breaking our child's accomplishments and cases together.

List of used literature

1. H.R.Turobova, M.U.Eshbekov. Improve children online safety//The multidisciplinary journal of science and technology. volume-3, issue-3. 2023. <https://mjstjournal.com/index.php/mjst/article/view/190/523>
2. Wurtele, S. K. Sexual interest in children among an online sample of men and women prevalence and correlates
3. . K.Wurtele, D. A. Simons. T. Moreno // Sexual Abuse A Journal of Research and Treatmentruen-2014-Vol 26, no. 6-P 546-568-
3. datareportal.com,
4. [Kun. uz](http://Kun.uz)
5. «[diaysuk. uz](http://diaysuk.uz)»
6. <https://www.theonespy.com/uz/>
7. <https://uzbekistan.ureport.in/>